

MICROMECHANICAL MODELLING OF DENSELY PACKED SYNTACTIC FOAM COMPOSITES

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1 Introduction

Composite foams filled with hollow microspheres, known as syntactic foams, are an efficient method to reduce weight in a high performance part without compromising to an excessive degree on mechanical properties. This makes them an attractive candidate for applications in across multiple sectors, including aerospace, marine, military and transport, where lightweight, load-bearing performance is crucial [1].

A micrograph of a syntactic foam consisting of an epoxy matrix reinforced with borosilicate glass is given in Figure 1. The microstructure clearly reveals three distinct phases, the epoxy matrix, the glass microsphere including the external shell and the internal void as well as some porosity external to the microspheres. It is clear that the microstructure of a syntactic is structurally complex, especially when the glass microspheres are densely packed together.

In the current work, we introduce a robust method for generating numerical models of syntactic foams up to a random close packed volume fraction of ~63 vol.%. The results of the numerical models are compared to experimental results. Remarkable agreement between the experimental results, not only in terms of the tensile modulus and characteristic strength, but also in terms of the degree of scatter of results as a function of volume fraction, as measured via the Weibull modulus.

2 Experimental Methods

2.1 Model Geometry and Finite Element Model

A common method used to study the micromechanics of particulate composite is to assume that the bulk behaviour can be adequately described by a regular arrangement of particles, e.g. [2]. This assumption of regularity, while providing detailed information on the interaction between particles, does not account for the variation in interparticle distance between particles in real composite. As a result, these models

are unable to capture experimentally observed variation in strength.

The Random Sequential adsorption algorithm is widely applied to generate random distributions of particles within a unit cell. It is efficient algorithm, elegant in its simplicity. However, it is unable to provide densely packed systems, or indeed volume fractions much in excess of 30 vol.%.

To obtain packing fractions approaching the random close packing limit, an approach based on molecular dynamics and first outlined by Lubachevsky and Stillinger is implemented [3].

Following the generation of densely packed arrangements of microspheres, a Python script was used to automate the pre- and post-processing of stochastic finite element models in Abaqus. Thirty random instantiations of representative elements containing 16 microspheres were calculated at each volume fraction. This provided enough information to statistically analyse the results. The stress and strain were calculate using a both a volumetric averaging approach and an approach based on direct calculation of the average tractions and strains on the loaded boundaries. A typical model geometry with a volume fraction of 60% of microspheres is given in Figure 2.

2.2 Experimental Methods

Samples of 10-30 vol.% microsphere were manufactured by first combining diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A to iso-phorone diamine in the stoichiometric ratio. The required amount of microspheres, type iM30k from 3M were then added and mixed until completely dispersed. The mixture was then degassed in a vacuum chamber to remove entrapped air and finally cast into a silicone mould.

3 Results

Figure 3 compares the experimental calculation of Young's modulus as measured via a uniaxial tensile

test versus the numerical predictions from the finite element model. Excellent agreement is observed.

Figure 4 compares the experimental measurements of fracture strength with the numerical, predictions. There is excellent agreement between measurements and predictions. Of particular interest is the capability of the numerical model to predict a large degree of scatter at low volume fractions with a reduction in this scatter as the volume fraction increases. This potentially indicates that the observed scatter in strength data can be attributed to the underlying randomness in the syntactic foam microstructure.

4 Conclusion

An automated numerical model for prediction of strength behaviour of syntactic foam has been developed. The model is able to recover the scatter typically observed in brittle fracture. Furthermore, the model can be used to inform design of syntactic foams, an important material for lightweight load bearing microstructures.

Fig.1. Scanning electron micrograph of a fractured syntactic foam sample.

Fig. 2. Exemplar numerical model with 60 vol. % microspheres.

Fig. 3. Comparison between experimental measurements and numerical predictions of Young's modulus.

Fig. 4. Comparison between experimental measurements and numerical predictions of fracture strength.

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